

Agronomic response, transpiration and water productivity of four almond production systems under different irrigation regimes

Manuel Quintanilla-Albornoz^{a,*}, Joaquim Bellvert^a, Ana Pelechá^a, Xavier Miarnau^b

^a Efficient Use of Water in Agriculture Program, Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology, Fruitcentre, Parc AgroBiotech, Lleida, 25003, Spain

^b Fruit Production Program, Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology, Fruitcentre, Parc AgroBiotech, Lleida, 25003, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Almond
Production systems
Sap flow
Remote sensing
Crop transpiration
Water productivity

ABSTRACT

In recent years, more intensive production systems have been developed, coinciding with a growing scarcity of water resources. This context underscores the imperative of prioritizing water productivity (WP) as a critical factor in choosing the optimal production system to minimize agricultural water use. This study aims to contribute by evaluating WP in almond orchards under four production systems: open vase with severe pruning (open vase), open vase with minimal pruning (open vase (MP)), central axis and hedgerow. Three irrigation treatments were applied over two consecutive growing seasons: fully irrigated, mild stress and severe stress. Crop transpiration was monitored over the two years using both sap flow sensors and the two-source energy balance (TSEB) model with remote sensing. The severe stress treatment exhibited a notable reduction in kernel yield and nut load of 31.6 % and 34.5 %, respectively, in the second year of water deficit. The hedgerow system tended to have similar kernel yield to the open vase (MP) and central axis systems, and higher compared to the open vase system. Additionally, both transpiration measurement methods revealed that hedgerow exhibited lower transpiration rates across all irrigation treatments. Therefore, the highest WP was observed in the hedgerow system throughout both studied years. Similar findings were derived from the analysis of long-term data. Our findings indicate that the hedgerow production system had the highest WP, averaging 0.43 kg m^{-3} historically, compared to 0.33 kg m^{-3} for the open vase, 0.34 kg m^{-3} for the open vase (MP), and 0.36 kg m^{-3} for the central axis systems.

1. Introduction

In the Mediterranean region, almond tree (*Prunus dulcis* (Mill.) D. A. Webb. syn. *Prunus Amygdalus* Batsch.) has traditionally been considered a social and unprofitable crop, mostly cultivated under rainfed conditions and marginal soils (Gradziel et al., 2017). Spain has the largest cultivated area of almond trees in the world but only ranks third in production, with an area of 878,075 ha an average yield of approximately 500 kg ha^{-1} of in-shell almonds (MAPA, 2023). These values contrast with those obtained in California and/or Australia, which exceed 2000 kg ha^{-1} of kernel yield. There is little doubt that the main difference between Spain and California/Australia almond yield per hectare lies in irrigation (USDA-NASS, 2022).

In Spain, irrigated almond has become more popular during recent decades, rising from 4.7 % of cultivated land in 2005 to 26 % in 2023 (180,562 ha) (MAPA, 2023). This increase in surface area has gone hand in hand with the introduction of new production systems (understood as

the interaction between rootstock, cultivar, training system and planting distance) capable of improving agronomic traits such as yield, precocity, and efficiency (Iglesias and Echeverria, 2022; Iglesias and Torrents, 2022; Maldera et al., 2021; Miarnau et al., 2022; Reig et al., 2020). It is well known that orchard intensification provides several advantages, including early bearing and lower labor costs due to mechanization (DeJong et al., 2005; Maldera et al., 2021). Furthermore, alternative novel architectures with higher densities and pruning methods that enhance light interception and distribution into the canopy have recently been developed, ensuring increased orchard profitability under new intensive production systems while reducing expenses (Iglesias and Echeverria, 2022). Nevertheless, one of the main concerns of high-density plantations is the higher initial investment as more trees are needed per hectare. The number of trees per hectare of a traditional almond plantation ($6 \times 6 \text{ m}$) has been estimated at around 278, whereas for high- and super high-density plantations the values can be as high as 666 and 2800 trees per hectare, respectively (Casanova-Gascón et al.,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: manuel.quintanilla@irta.cat (M. Quintanilla-Albornoz).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2024.113335>

Received 23 March 2024; Received in revised form 9 May 2024; Accepted 20 May 2024

Available online 30 May 2024

0304-4238/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

2019; Miarnau et al., 2022).

The transition towards more intensive crop growing is occurring at the same time as water resources are becoming scarcer due to droughts and climate change, especially in the Mediterranean region (Tramblay et al., 2020; Gaona et al., 2022). The gradual depletion of water reserves has emerged as a significant concern in the agricultural sector, prompting regulatory authorities to implement water supply restrictions and rationing measures throughout the Mediterranean region. For example, many irrigation districts located in the Ebro basin (Spain) were forced to impose water restrictions during 2023 without distinction between crops to ensure the survival of fruit tree crops. In the particular case of the Segarra-Garrigues (Lleida, Spain) irrigation district, water rights for almonds in 2023 were established at $1350 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$, which corresponded to a water restriction of around 80 % ($6500 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ in full water allocation conditions) (ASG, 2023).

In this context, the promotion of almond orchards with production systems with a higher agricultural water productivity (WP) is crucial to mitigate the effects of climate change. WP has usually been determined as the ratio between yield and the amount of irrigation water applied (Feres and Soriano, 2007; López-López et al., 2018; Moldero et al., 2021). However, maximizing WP requires both an accounting of water consumed through irrigation and an understanding of the crop yield-evapotranspiration relationship. In this regard, numerous studies have assessed the effect of adopting regulated deficit irrigation (RDI) strategies to improve agricultural WP, showing in general that RDI strategies in almonds could be beneficial for WP maximization (Egea et al., 2010; Goldhamer and Feres, 2017; López-López et al., 2018). Although some studies indicated that the adoption of RDI strategies may result in a 20 % reduction in yield, the substantial water saving of 60 % indicates that RDI remains a promising option in water-constrained areas (Girona et al., 2005). In addition of the adoption of RDI strategies, WP could potentially be improved through the development of new production systems. The crop water requirements are strongly affected by canopy size (Espadafor et al., 2015; Jofre-Čekalović et al., 2022). Therefore, among the different parameters involved in a production system, the selection of an appropriate training system and an ideal planting distance probably could have the highest impact on transpiration, and as a consequence, WP. Some studies have compared canopy light interception, as a proxy of transpiration, between training systems in woody crops (Auzmendi et al., 2023). These concluded that open-center or 3D canopy systems had a higher light interception than planar designs such as palmettes and central leader canopy structures (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019; Iglesias and Echeverria, 2022). This study also described that almonds under an open-center vase system had higher kernel yields in comparison to a super high-density system (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019). However, other studies have reported that more intense production systems exhibit higher yield per canopy volume, therefore improving yield efficiency due to more efficient use of light (Ben Yahmed et al., 2016; Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019).

WP can also be derived as the ratio between yield and unit of water consumed by a crop (transpiration) (Fernández, 2023). Although this methodology is not widely used due to the difficulties of monitoring canopy transpiration, this option seems to be more appropriate to assess differences between crops or production systems, because part of the water supplied by precipitation and irrigation can be lost to drainage and runoff. Among the different techniques used to monitor transpiration, sap flow sensors and remote sensing are the two most promising for the purpose of the present study. Sap flow sensors have significant benefits as they measure transpiration in an easy-to-use, continuous, automated manner with a high temporal resolution (Smith and Allen, 1996; Fernández et al., 2001; López-Bernal et al., 2010; Noun et al., 2022). For their part, remote sensing thermal-based surface energy balance (SEB) models have also been shown to be favorable for the estimation of evapotranspiration (ET) fluxes in a wide range of ecosystems, monitoring heterogeneous surfaces and generating operational ET products (Allen et al., 2007; Drexler et al., 2004; Kalma et al., 2008;

Overgaard et al., 2006; Shuttleworth and Wallace, 1985). Among the different SEB models, the two-source energy balance (TSEB) model (Norman et al., 1995) is the most widely used approach, in part because it can estimate canopy transpiration and soil evaporation separately. Studies have demonstrated the suitability of using this modelling approach with very high-resolution imagery acquired from an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) to assess crop ET at field scale (Peddinti and Kisekka, 2022; Gao et al., 2023; Ramírez-Cuesta et al., 2023) or for field-based phenotyping purposes (Bellvert et al., 2021; Gómez-Candón et al., 2023).

To our knowledge, no study has directly assessed the WP of different almond production systems by monitoring canopy transpiration. Only a recent study by Quintanilla-Albornoz et al. (2023) demonstrated that transpiration estimates of almonds through the combined use of a TSEB contextual approach and an adapted version of the Campbell and Norman radiation transmittance model for rectangular hedgerow crops had an overall coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.77 and root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.13 mm h^{-1} . This study aims to go a step further and determine the WP of 12-year-old almond trees with different training systems and planting distances subjected to diverse irrigation regimes during two consecutive growing seasons. For this purpose, transpiration was monitored through two methodologies in order to confirm the robustness of the results: sap flow sensors and the remote sensing TSEB modelling approach. Additionally, a retrospective evaluation of WP will be undertaken over a long-term period.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Trial location and design

This research was conducted at the experimental station of IRTA (Institute of Research and Technology, Food and Agriculture) in Les Borges Blanques, Spain ($41^{\circ}30'31.89''\text{N}$; $0^{\circ}51'10.70''\text{E}$, 323 m elevation) (Fig. 1a,b). The almond orchard, planted in June 2009, features “Marinada” as the scion cultivar grafted onto ‘INRA GF-677’ rootstock and incorporates four distinct training systems and planting distance combinations. Henceforth, in this manuscript, the term “production system” will be used to denote the combination of training system and planting distance. The following production systems were assessed: open vase with severe pruning (referred to as open vase in following lines) with a planting distance of $6 \times 6 \text{ m}$, open vase with minimal pruning (referred to as open vase (MP) in the following lines) with $5.5 \times 3.5 \text{ m}$, central axis with $5 \times 3 \text{ m}$, and hedgerow with $4.5 \times 3 \text{ m}$ (Fig. 1c). The soil texture of the study site was classified as clay-loamy, with a depth ranging between 1.6 and 2 m. The climate in the study site corresponds to Mediterranean, with an average annual rainfall of 360.3 mm and an average annual evapotranspiration of 1090 mm. Table 1 shows the annual cumulative reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) and precipitation (PP) from 2011 to 2022, sourced from a weather station located at 500 m from the study site, with code “les Borges Blanques [YD]”, in Catalonia’s official network of meteorological stations (SMC, www.ruralcat.net/web/guest/agrometeo). Fig. 2 illustrates the daily values of ET_o, PP, vapor pressure deficit (VPD), and minimum and maximum air temperature (T_{\min} and T_{\max}) throughout 2021 and 2022 seasons. A frost event was recorded on March 20th 2021 and April 5th 2022, with a T_{\min} of -3.3°C and -3.9°C , respectively. These events coincided with the full flowering stage of almond trees in both years.

The orchard was irrigated using a drip irrigation system. The irrigation system for both the open vase and open vase (MP) systems involved two lateral pipes positioned on each side of the tree at 40 cm, with drippers spaced every 70 cm and a water discharge of 2.2 l h^{-1} . The central axis and hedgerow had only one lateral pipe along with the row line, with drippers positioned every 60 cm and a water discharge of 3.8 l h^{-1} per dripper. Prior to 2021, the orchard was irrigated daily seeking to replace crop evapotranspiration (ET_C) as follows: $ET_C = (ET_o \times K_c \times K_r) - \text{effective rainfall}$. K_c and K_r represent the crop coefficient and shading

Fig. 1. (a) Location of the studied almond orchard located in Les Borges Blanques (Lleida, Spain), (b) RGB orthomosaic of the almond orchard, and (c) Photographs from winter 2011 (top) and summer 2022 (bottom) and description of the different production systems assessed in the trial.

Table 1
Cumulative annual reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) and cumulative annual precipitation (PP) for the period 2011–2022.

Year	ET _o (mm)	PP (mm)
2011	1095.1	294.4
2012	1096.1	303.0
2013	1072.5	435.4
2014	1074.1	425.7
2015	1101.6	185.9
2016	1080.2	352.9
2017	1099.7	290.0
2018	1059.9	535.3
2019	1132.6	377.2
2020	1070.9	475.8
2021	1065.3	288.7
2022	1132.5	317.5
Mean	1090.0	360.3

factor, respectively. The Penman-Monteith method was used to determine ET_o (Allen et al., 1998). The K_c values were derived from Goldhamer and Snyder (1989), who estimate the following K_c values at different phenological stages in almonds trees under the open vase

training system: K_{c1} = 0.70 (April), K_{c1} = 0.95 (May), K_{c2} = 1.09 (June), K_{c3} = 1.15 (July), K_{c4} = 1.17 (August), and K_{c5} = 1.12 (September). Kr was determined as a function of canopy size of the trees, following Fereres et al. (1981). A Kr value of 0.98 was calculated for the entire orchard, considering the size of the trees in the open vase production system. To address potential uncertainties regarding different water requirement among production systems, irrigation was also adjusted to ensure that the stem water potential of fully irrigated trees remained above -1.0 MPa (Girona et al., 2006). Effective rainfall was estimated as half of the rainfall for a single event-day with more than 10 mm of precipitation and otherwise was considered to be zero (Olivo et al., 2009).

During 2021 and 2022, each production system was divided into three irrigation treatments: (i) Fully irrigated, where irrigation was aimed at fulfilling tree ET requirements (100 % ET_C) throughout the growing season; (ii) mild stress, with irrigation maintained at 50 % ET_C throughout the growing season; and (iii) severe stress, with irrigation limited to 20 % ET_C throughout the growing season. A split-block design was used in this experiment. Each block treatment consisted of 6 trees (3 × 2). The amount of water applied to each treatment was measured with digital water meters (CZ2000-3 M, Contazara, Zaragoza, Spain), as

Fig. 2. Seasonal evolution of daily reference evapotranspiration (ETo), daily cumulative precipitation (PP), daily vapor pressure deficit (VPD), and daily minimum and maximum air temperature (T_{min} and T_{max}) during 2021 and 2022.

detailed in Table 2.

2.2. Physiological and structural measurements

2.2.1. Stem water potential

The midday stem water potential (Ψ_s) was measured every two weeks using the protocol outlined by McCutchan and Shackel (1992). In each production system, two trees were measured for each irrigation treatment during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons. The measured trees were the same where the sap flow sensors were installed in the open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow systems. Three leaves of each tree were measured to estimate Ψ_s . Shaded leaves were selected and placed in a bag covered with aluminum foil for 1 hour before measurement to balance the water potential between leaf, stem and branches. All leaves were measured within 1 hour using a pressure chamber (Plant Water Status Console, Model 3500; Soil Moisture

Table 2
Seasonal water applied through irrigation in each of the three irrigation treatments in each production system during 2021 and 2022.

Production System	Irrigation Treatment	Irrigation (mm)	
		2021	2022
Open Vase	Fully Irrigated	727	861
	Mild Stress	355	404
	Severe Stress	140	201
Open Vase (MP)	Fully Irrigated	837	1093
	Mild Stress	414	464
	Severe Stress	177	258
Central Axis	Fully Irrigated	741	863
	Mild Stress	394	429
	Severe Stress	152	201
Hedgerow	Fully Irrigated	850	992
	Mild Stress	390	475
	Severe Stress	175	255

Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, CA). The integrated stem water potential (Int(Ψ_s)) was estimated to account for both the intensity and the duration of water stress. Int(Ψ_s) was calculated using Eq.1, as defined by Myers (1998).

$$Int(\Psi_s) = \left| \sum_{i=0}^{i=t} (\Psi_{i, i+1} - \Psi_{max})n \right| \tag{1}$$

where $\Psi_{i, i+1}$ represents the average of Ψ_s between two consecutive measurement days, n is the number of days in the measurement period, and Ψ_{max} is the maximum Ψ_s measured during the season.

2.2.2. Fraction of intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (fIPAR)

The diurnal evolution of the fraction of intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (fIPAR) was measured in three trees of each production system, one per irrigation treatment, for the dates May 26th (shell growth period), June 29th (early kernel filling period) and July 29th of 2021 (kernel filling period). The methodology described by Casadesús et al. (2011) was followed. In each tree, fixed 125 cm long sensor bars containing photodiodes every 10 cm (VTB8440BH, PerkinElmer Optoelectronics, Vaudreuil, Canada) were installed. Each photodiode is installed in an aluminum channel with the outer section of 25 mm and covered by a 4.6 mm thick PTFE sheath (TECAFLON PTFE, Ensinger Ltd., Llantrisant, UK) that acted as a light diffuser. The photodiodes have a spectral response ranging from 330 to 720 nm wavelengths, with a peak at 580 nm, corresponding to the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) region. The sensing bars were positioned parallel to the crop rows, covering the entire distances between trees. Because of the varying planting distances among the production systems, 10 sensing bars were installed in the open vase and open vase (MP) systems, while 5 were installed in the central axis and hedgerow systems. Reference measurements of PAR above the canopy (PAR_{above}) were obtained by using two sensing bars placed outside the field (uncovered)

to measure direct incident PAR. The PAR below the canopy (PAR_{below}) was measured using bars installed on the ground of the planting system. The PAR data was recorded every 10 min. The fIPAR was calculated as follows: $1 - (PAR_{\text{below}}/PAR_{\text{above}})$. The daily average fIPAR (fIPARd) was then obtained based on measurements recorded during daylight hours.

2.2.3. Transpiration from sap flow sensors

In situ transpiration was monitored in the open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow production systems using sap flow sensors. Regrettably, open vase sap flow data was not used due to technical issues. In these production systems, two trees of the fully irrigated and severe stress treatments and one tree in the mild stress treatment were monitored with sap flows. Sap flows were installed at 0.5 m above the ground. Sap flow transpiration measurements (T-SF) were corrected for wounding and azimuthal effects (López-Bernal et al., 2010). The sap flow sensor uses the compensation heat pulse (CHP) and the calibrated average gradient method. The used sap flows were developed by the IAS-CSIC laboratory. The sap flow sensors consist of a 2 mm diameter 4.8-W stainless steel heater and two temperature sensors positioned 10 and 5 mm downstream and upstream of the heater, respectively. Both temperature sensors contain two embedded type E (chromel–constantan wire) thermocouples spaced 1 mm along the needle. The sap flux densities across the trunk radius are calculated based on the heat-pulse velocities at 5 and 15 mm below the cambium. For further specifications, see Villalobos et al. (2009). Sap flow data was recorded every 15 min using a CR1000 datalogger (Campbell Scientific Inc., Logan, UT, USA). The correction coefficient was obtained from in situ measurements of transpiration obtained from a water balance method using Eq. 2 (López-López et al., 2018):

$$T_{\text{wb}} = PP + IR - \Delta\text{SWC} - DP - E_s \quad (2)$$

where T_{wb} is daily transpiration obtained by the water balance, PP is precipitation, IR is the amount of water applied through irrigation, ΔSWC is the difference in soil water content (SWC) between two consecutive days, DP is deep percolation and E_s corresponds to evaporation. The water balance was calculated during three days without PP or IR application. Therefore, the parameters PP, DP and IR were considered null. The soil was covered with a plastic sheet to prevent E_s fluxes during sap flow calibration.

The SWC was measured using a neutron probe (Campbell Pacific Nuclear Scientific, Model 503) every 20 cm to a depth of 180 cm. At the time of tube installation, soil samples were collected to measure the actual volumetric moisture content (cm^3 of water/ cm^3 of soil) for calibration of the neutron probe measurements. Six tubes were installed in one quarter of the planting area in each tree. Tube distribution corresponded to two sets of three tubes (6 tubes in total) placed beneath the emitter, one set at a quarter and the other at half of the distance between rows. Calibration coefficients determined from T_{wb} and T-SF measurements were assumed to remain constant throughout the entire growing season, as demonstrated by Espadafor et al. (2015). The calibrated T-SF was used to calculate cumulative daily and seasonal transpiration.

Daily and seasonal transpiration of the open vase trees, the production system without sap flow sensors, and using two trees in each irrigation treatment for 2021 and 2022 was estimated as follows: $\text{Transpiration} = ETo \times Ka$. Ka corresponds to the ratio between actual transpiration and ETo. A multi-regression model was used to retrieve the actual crop coefficient (Ka). This model was trained using all the available data from sap flow sensors installed in the open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow production systems, as well as the fractional canopy cover (fc) and Ψ_s measured values. fc was used on the principle that it correlates well with the transpiration coefficient (K_T) (Espadafor et al., 2015). Additionally, the same methodology was applied to retrieve transpiration of all trees during the period 2016 to 2020 and for the remaining trees that had no sap flow sensors during 2021 and 2022. In this case, it was assumed that fc did not change over the six years in

question and trees were fully irrigated. Therefore, Ka was calculated using the average fc of all trees during 2021 and Ψ_s values of the fully irrigated treatment.

2.3. Transpiration from remote sensing

2.3.1. Image acquisition campaign

The image acquisition campaign consisted of five flights carried out in 2021 (March 24th, May 19th, June 3rd and 29th, and July 29th), and four in 2022 (May 27th, June 29th, and August 1st and 19th). The flights were conducted with a UAV Dronehexa XL (DRONETOOLS, Seville, Spain) equipped with a Micasense RedEdge-MX multispectral camera (Micasense, Northlake Way, Seattle, USA) and a FLIR SC655 thermal camera (FLIR Systems, Wilsonville, OR, USA). The Micasense Red-Edge-MX captures images in five spectral bands, with wavelengths of 475 ± 20 nm, 560 ± 20 nm, 668 ± 10 nm, 717 ± 10 nm, and 840 ± 40 nm. The FLIR SC655 responds within the 7.5–13 μm spectrum. The flights were carried out at 50 m above ground level in order to obtain multispectral and thermal images with spatial resolutions of 0.03 m and 0.06 m, respectively.

All images were subjected to radiometric, atmospheric and geometric correction. The Jaz spectrometer (Ocean Optics, Inc., Dunedin, FL, USA) was used to collect in situ spectral measurements on several ground targets in parallel with the image acquisition for radiometric calibration. The Jaz has a wavelength response from 200 to 1100 nm and an optical resolution of 0.3–10.0 nm. The spectrometer was calibrated using a white reference panel (white color Spectralon™) before spectral measurements. The thermal sensor was calibrated in the laboratory with a blackbody (model P80P, Land Instruments, Dronfield, United Kingdom). In addition, in situ temperature measurements were collected using an SI-111-SS Apogee infrared radiometer connected to an Apogee AT-100 microCache Bluetooth micrologger (Apogee Instruments Inc, Logan, UT, USA). The mosaicking process and generation of the digital elevation model (DEM) and digital surface models (DSM) from point clouds of the multispectral images were performed with the Agisoft Metashape Professional software (Agisoft LLC., St. Petersburg, Russia), while QGIS 3.4 (QGIS 3.4.15) was used for the geometric and radiometric corrections.

2.3.2. Biophysical traits

The canopy area, canopy width, canopy height, fc , canopy volume, canopy temperature (T_c) and soil temperature (T_s) were obtained for all almond trees using a supervised image classification based on the use of the DSM and the soil-adjusted vegetation index (SAVI). SAVI was chosen because it increases the contrast between vegetation and the soil surface by reducing the impact of soil brightness in the red and near-infrared wavelengths (Qi et al., 1994). Pixels were classified as canopy when having DSM values greater than 1.5 m and SAVI values greater than 0.2. Pixels that did not meet the conditions were categorized as pure soil.

The canopy area was estimated as the sum of the area of the pixels classified as canopy. Canopy volume was estimated as the product of canopy area and canopy height. In addition, the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) (Jackson and Huete, 1991), the normalized difference water index (NDWI) (McFeeters, 1996) and the modified triangular vegetation index (MTVI2) (Xing et al., 2020) were also calculated. These parameters were used as additional inputs of a machine learning approach to estimate the leaf area index (LAI) using a random forest algorithm (scikit-learn Python library) and following the methodology described by Quintanilla-Albornoz et al. (2023) in a study which demonstrated that this approach was able to estimate the LAI with an RMSE of $0.30 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$. The extraction of biophysical traits from high resolution images was conducted using the Python programming language (Python Software Foundation. Python Language Reference version 3.10. available at <http://www.python.org>).

2.3.3. TSEB model description

Transpiration was also estimated for all almond trees with the contextual TSEB model using high-resolution thermal and multispectral imagery (Nieto et al., 2019). TSEB is based on an energy balance approach that assumes that the surface net canopy radiation (R_n) is distributed mainly between sensible heat flux (H), latent heat flux (LE) and soil heat flux (G). Therefore, LE ($W\ m^{-2}$) can be calculated as a residual of the surface energy equation (Kustas and Anderson, 2009; Norman et al., 1995). To retrieve transpiration, the canopy and soil R_n were estimated using the canopy radiative transfer model of Campbell and Norman (1998). To estimate canopy transmittance, a basic clumping index was assumed for the open vase system. Meanwhile, a rectangular hedgerow clumping index was applied to the open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow systems, following the procedure outlined by Quintanilla-Albornoz et al. (2023). The contextual TSEB approach was applied with direct measurement of T_c and T_s from high-resolution thermal images. To estimate daily transpiration (T-TSEB) from the instantaneous TSEB estimations, the simulated evaporative fraction variable method was used (Hoedjes et al., 2008; Quintanilla-Albornoz et al., 2024).

2.4. Production and kernel quality parameters

Harvesting was conducted by shaking trees with commercial equipment and then picking up almonds from the ground. After that, nuts were dehulled and their in-shell fresh weight per tree measured, calculating the gross yield. To determine the dry kernel weight, a 1 kg in-shell nut sample for each replicate/tree was naturally dried until the moisture content in the kernel reached 6 %. The shelling percentage (kernel weight/in-shell weight) was obtained by measuring the dry weight of the in-shell nut and kernel from a sample of 100 nuts. Finally, the kernel yield ($kg\ ha^{-1}$) was computed by multiplying the shelling percentage by the in-shell nut yield. The estimated kernel yield per canopy volume was calculated by dividing the kernel yield of the tree by its estimated canopy volume. The nut load was measured by dividing the total kernel yield by the average kernel weight.

2.5. Water productivity (WP)

The WP was calculated by dividing kernel yield by transpiration. For the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons, WP was assessed using the following two methodologies: (1) seasonal cumulative T-SF data for all production systems, with the partial exception of the open vase which was modelled using a multi-regression model (WP-SF); and (2) using the averaged estimated daily transpiration through the TSEB model of all image acquisition dates in each year (WP-TSEB). The difference between these two methodologies is that in the first only very few trees were monitored with sap flow sensors, while in the second a more representative information was obtained for each treatment/production system since transpiration was estimated for six trees in each. Additionally, WP was also estimated for the period 2016–2020 using historical kernel yield data. In this case, transpiration was obtained for all trees in each production system using the multi-regression modelling approach previously explained to retrieve the K_a . WP was not estimated prior to 2016 due to the lack of information regarding biophysical traits, and therefore it was assumed that canopy volume did not significantly change between the 2016 and 2021.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The data collected was analyzed with a three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the JMP Pro-Software (version 16.0, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC). A final mixed model including production systems, irrigation treatments and their interaction as fixed factors, and block nested to date (year or day depending on the analysis) as a random factor was used to separate the treatment effects from the data. Tukey's

HSD test was used to compare treatments for all production systems when the source effect was significant, with p -values ≤ 0.05 .

3. Results

3.1. Stem water potential as water status indicator

Fig. 3 illustrates the seasonal pattern of stem water potential (Ψ_s) during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons. The $\text{Int}(\Psi_s)$ exhibited a significant response between years, production systems, irrigation treatments, and the interaction between production system and irrigation treatment (PSxTRT) was also significant (Table 3). Overall, Ψ_s for the fully irrigated treatment was relatively constant during both growing seasons, with values above -1.0 MPa, with the partial exception of two dates. These two dates correspond to June 19th 2022 (DOY 170, shell growth period) and August 19th 2022 (DOY 231, kernel filling period), where minimum Ψ_s values were recorded for all irrigation treatments and production systems. These lower values for the two dates of 2022 explained, in part, the statistical significance between years. The severe stress treatment showed the lowest values throughout both growing seasons. Ψ_s started declining at the beginning of the growing season, with values always below -1.3 MPa from June 15th (DOY 166, early kernel filling period), with the partial exception of the open vase production system. Although irrigation was also reduced in the severe stress treatment of the open vase system, Ψ_s did not decline as much as in the other systems. The mild stress treatment always maintained intermediate values. Table 4 shows a summary of the $\text{Int}(\Psi_s)$ values, comparing differences between the production systems in each irrigation treatment. Open vase was the production system with the lowest values in all irrigation treatments.

3.2. Biophysical traits

The biophysical variables fc , canopy height, canopy volume and LAI showed significant differences between years, production systems and in the interaction between production system and year (PSxYear), and PSxTRT (Table 3). Open vase (MP) exhibited the highest fc in all irrigated treatments, which ranged from 55 to 69 % depending on the treatment (Table 4). Conversely, hedgerow had the lowest fc , ranging from 47 to 52 % also depending on the irrigation treatment. Central axis had a higher fc than open vase for all treatments. Canopy height was higher in 2022 than in 2021. Similarly to fc , open vase (MP) had the tallest trees and hedgerow the lowest. On the other hand, open vase had the highest canopy volume in all irrigation treatments, ranging between 78.9 and 102.8 m^3 . In contrast, the central axis and hedgerow systems displayed the smallest canopy volume in all irrigation treatments, with values ranging from 26.8 to 38.4 m^3 . Although LAI was the only variable that did not show significant differences between irrigation treatments, the interaction PSxTRTxYear was slightly significant. This explains that all the production systems under full irrigation had a higher LAI than other irrigation treatments, except for hedgerow. On average, open vase had significantly lower values in comparison to the other production systems. These differences were more evident in the severe stress irrigation treatment.

The fIPAR exhibited a significant variation with production system, irrigation treatment and PSxTRT (Table 3). Significant differences in irrigation treatments were observed between open vase and open vase (MP), while no significant differences were detected between central axis and hedgerow across irrigation treatments. Overall, open vase (MP) showed a significantly higher fIPARd, with a daily mean value of 0.62. The open vase system had the lowest fIPARd, with a mean value of 0.54. The other two production systems showed intermediate values (Table 4). The diurnal course of fIPAR for each production system is shown in Fig. 4. The statistical analysis showed a significant interaction between production system and hour (p -value < 0.001). The significantly lower values of the open vase system were observed during the

Fig. 3. Seasonal patterns of midday stem water potential (Ψ_s) for the production systems: (a) Open Vase; (b) Open Vase (MP); (c) Central Axis; and (d) Hedgerow, in the different irrigation treatments (fully irrigated, mild stress and severe stress) during the growing seasons 2021 and 2022.

Table 3

Analysis of variance (three-way ANOVA) to assess the effect of year, production system (PS) and irrigation treatment (TRT) on the integrated stem water potential (Int (Ψ_s)), the biophysical traits: fractional cover (f_c), canopy height, canopy volume, leaf area index (LAI), and daily fraction of intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (fIPARd), seasonal cumulative daily transpiration from sap flow sensors (T-SF) and averaged daily transpiration from remote sensing using the TSEB modelling approach (T-TSEB).

Source	Year	PS	TRT	PSxYear	TRTxYear	PSxTRT	PSxTRTxYear
Int(Ψ_s)	0.005	<0.0001	<0.0001	ns	ns	0.0082	ns
f_c	0.0382	<0.0001	0.0002	0.0276	ns	0.0076	ns
Canopy Height	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	ns	0.046	ns
Canopy Volume	0.0037	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	ns	0.0002	ns
LAI	<0.0001	<0.0001	ns	<0.0001	ns	0.0359	0.0063
fIPARd	–	<0.0001	<0.0001	–	–	0.0002	–
T-SF	ns	<0.0001	<0.0001	ns	ns	ns	ns
T-TSEB	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0248	ns	0.0039	ns

morning, from 7:00 to 11:00 (solar time), and also during the afternoon (from 14:00 to 15:00). It can also be observed how the decline of fIPAR of the hedgerow production system was more pronounced during the morning until reaching its minimum values between 12:00 and 14:00, coinciding with the peak of solar radiation. At this time, however, no significant differences were observed in fIPAR between production systems. During the afternoon, central axis and open vase (MP) exhibited significantly higher fIPAR than hedgerow and open vase.

3.3. Transpiration from sap flow sensors

The multi-regression model developed to simulate daily

transpiration for the open vase production system yielded the following equation: $K_a = 1.21 f_c - 0.24 \Psi_s$, where Ψ_s is in MPa. The R^2 , RMSE and bias were respectively 0.61, 0.124 and 0.01. The ANOVA analysis to evaluate seasonal cumulative T-SF revealed significant differences between production systems and between treatments, but not in their interaction (Table 3). The seasonal pattern of T-SF for fully irrigated trees had a trend similar to E_{To} , reaching the maximum values during July coinciding with dates with a higher E_{To} and canopy growth (Fig. 5). At this time, maximum T-SF values reached 7 mm day^{-1} for open vase (MP) and central axis, and 5 mm day^{-1} for open vase and hedgerow. During August and September, T-SF started progressively decreasing in all treatments with E_{To} and leaf senescence. In contrast, almond trees

Table 4

Comparison of integrated stem water potential ($\text{Int}(\Psi_s)$) and the main biophysical traits estimated and measured during the image acquisition campaign for the different production systems and irrigation treatments: fractional cover (f_c), canopy height, canopy volume, leaf area index (LAI) and daily fraction of intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (fIPARd), and seasonal cumulative daily transpiration from sap flow sensors (T-SF) and averaged daily transpiration from remote sensing using the TSEB modelling approach (T-TSEB). Different letters in each mean indicate significant differences at p-value < 0.05 using Tukey's honest significant difference test and considering the interaction between production system and irrigation treatment. Values corresponds to mean values of the two years.

Irrigation Treatment	Production System	Int(Ψ_s)	f_c (%)	Canopy Height (m)	Canopy Volume (m^3)	LAI ($\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$)	fIPARd	T-SF (mm year^{-1})	T-TSEB (mm day^{-1})
Fully Irrigated	Open Vase	144.4 b	53 c	5.25 b	102.8 a	3.24 b	0.53 c	641.2 a	5.29 ab
	Open Vase (MP)	243.4 ab	62 a	5.60 a	67.87 b	3.58 a	0.64 a	765.7 a	6.14 a
	Central Axis	326.8 a	55 b	4.40 c	36.9 c	3.42 ab	0.61 ab	610.7 a	5.45 ab
	Hedgerow	330.8 a	47 d	4.22 c	26.8 c	3.38 b	0.55 bc	541.1 b	4.51 b
Mild Stress	Open Vase	205.7 c	51 b	5.28 a	97.8 a	3.16 c	0.60 b	668.0 a	5.05 ab
	Open Vase (MP)	562.9 a	69 a	5.61 a	74.94 b	3.52 a	0.66 a	654.2 a	5.80 a
	Central Axis	652.7 a	57 b	4.46 b	38.4 c	3.23 b	0.59 b	532.9 b	4.91 ab
	Hedgerow	380.8 b	52 c	4.22 c	33.7 c	3.53 a	0.59 b	430.3 c	4.42 b
Severe Stress	Open Vase	228.7 b	46 b	4.75 b	78.9 a	2.9 c	0.50 b	509.6 a	4.72 a
	Open Vase (MP)	761.2 a	55 a	5.17 a	55.3 b	3.29 b	0.58 a	545.3 a	3.99 ab
	Central Axis	827.7 a	53 a	3.92 d	30.3 c	3.20 b	0.59 a	427.5 b	3.04 b
	Hedgerow	786.3 a	47 b	4.21 c	28.8 c	3.60 a	0.58 a	352.7 c	3.28 b

Fig. 4. Daily evolution of the hourly fraction of intercepted photosynthetically active radiation (fIPAR) for each production system. Each value corresponds to the mean of one tree measured hourly (solar time) in each irrigation treatment for dates May 26th, June 29th and July 29th in 2021. Different letters indicate significant differences between production systems within each hour at p-value < 0.05 using Tukey's test. Grey dashed line corresponds to hourly solar radiation during measured days.

under the severe stress treatment reached peak T-SF around the second week of May, after which it gradually declined. The T-SF pattern in the mild stress treatment was similar to that in fully irrigated in the open vase and open vase (MP) systems. In central axis and hedgerow, the values were intermediate with the maximum reached around mid-June.

Seasonal cumulative T-SF presented significant differences between production systems and irrigation treatments (Table 3). The hedgerow system significantly transpired less under the three irrigation treatments (Table 4), presenting the lowest T-SF with a mean of 441.4 mm year^{-1} compared to the 532.7 mm year^{-1} for the central axis system. However, open vase and open vase (MP) had the highest T-SF with 618.1 mm

year^{-1} and 643.2 mm year^{-1} , respectively. T-SF clearly differed between irrigation treatments, where fully irrigated, mild stress and severe stress exhibited T-SF values of 639.7 mm year^{-1} , 571.3 mm year^{-1} and 458.8 mm year^{-1} , respectively.

3.4. Transpiration from remote sensing

The T-TSEB exhibited significant differences between years, production systems and irrigation treatments, and in the PSxYear and PSxTRT interactions (Table 3). The relationship between seasonal cumulative T-SF and the mean T-TSEB for the nine image acquisition dates

Fig. 5. Seasonal pattern of daily transpiration measured with sap flows for the different production systems: (a) and (b) Open Vase; (c) and (d) Open Vase (MP); (e) and (f) Central Axis; and (g) and (h) Hedgerow, in different irrigation treatments (fully irrigated, mild stress and severe stress) during the growing seasons 2021 (left) and 2022 (right). A multiple regression model was used to estimate transpiration in the open vase system.

showed a positive regression with an R^2 of 0.49 and a Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.70. Open vase exhibited the highest T-TSEB under the severe stress treatment, whereas the open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow displayed no significant differences in the severe stress treatment. However, the open vase (MP) production system had the highest transpiration rates in both the fully irrigated and the mild stress irrigation treatments. This confirms the results obtained with T-

SF. The lowest T-TSEB values under both full irrigation and mild stress conditions were observed in the hedgerow system. Significant differences were observed in the open vase system between years, with mean estimated transpiration values of 4.21 mm day^{-1} and 5.82 mm day^{-1} for 2021 and 2022, respectively.

3.5. Yield and yield components

Kernel yield showed significant differences between years and production systems and in the PSxYear interaction (Table 5). It is important to note that the two years of study were affected by significant frosts during late winter, which caused production to fall below the average of the previous years. Open vase significantly showed the lowest kernel yield values in 2021 (1062 kg ha⁻¹) and 2022 (696 kg ha⁻¹) (Table 6). In 2021, the other three production systems showed higher kernel yields, but without significant differences between them. Open vase (MP) was the only system that had a significantly higher kernel yield in 2022 (1747 kg ha⁻¹). No significant differences in kernel yield were observed between irrigation treatments (Table 5).

Kernel yield per canopy volume showed significant variations between years and production systems and in the PSxYear interaction. Open vase had the lowest kernel yield per canopy volume in 2021 (0.037 kg m⁻³) and in 2022 (0.024 kg m⁻³). Conversely, the hedgerow system consistently yielded significantly higher kernel yield per canopy volume in both years. However, the open vase (MP) system showed a kernel yield per canopy volume similar to that of hedgerow in 2022.

Shelling percentage showed significant variations between production systems and irrigation treatments. The lowest shelling percentage was observed in the hedgerow system, with a two-year average of 29.71 % (Table 6). Shelling percentage was significantly higher in the full irrigation treatment (32.84 %), while the two-year average for the mild and severe stress treatments was 31.78 % and 30.33 %, respectively.

Significant differences in kernel weight were observed with respect to year, production system, irrigation treatment and the PSxYear interaction (Table 5). Kernel weight of fully irrigated and mild stress irrigation treatments were significantly higher than in the severe stress treatment. With a mean kernel weight of 1.76 g, open vase had the highest weight in both years. In contrast, significant differences were observed between years in the hedgerow production system, where average kernel weight was 1.42 g in 2021 in comparison to 1.56 g in 2022. As a result, hedgerow had the lowest kernel weight with an average of 1.49 g (Table 6).

Nut load yielded significant differences by year, production system and the PSxYear interaction (Table 5). In 2021, the hedgerow system yielded the highest nut load, whereas in 2022 the highest nut load was observed in open vase (MP). In contrast, open vase had the lowest number of nuts per hectare in 2022, with a total of 386,965 nuts ha⁻¹. Therefore, hedgerow and open vase (MP) showed the highest nut loads with an average of 926,069 nuts ha⁻¹ and 953,732 nuts ha⁻¹ and, respectively.

3.6. Almond water productivity

The WP was calculated using the two methodologies to obtain transpiration, with sap flow sensors and remote sensing. Both approaches exhibited significant differences between years, production systems and in the PSxYear interaction. The only difference between the approaches was that the first (WP-SF) was not significant between irrigation treatments and in the TRTxYear interaction (Table 5). WP-SF had a significantly higher value in the hedgerow production system for the

two evaluated years (0.40 and 0.24 kg m⁻³ for 2021 and 2022, respectively), although with the biggest differences in 2021 (Fig. 6). During 2022, despite having a higher WP-SF, the value was similar to that of open vase (MP) and central axis. On average, the lowest WP-SF for the two years was observed in the open vase system (0.15 kg m⁻³).

The WP-TSEB results were similar but not identical to those for WP-SF. On average, open vase was also the production system with the lowest WP-TSEB, mostly due to lower values in 2022. The hedgerow system displayed the highest WP-TSEB in both years, although higher in 2021. Significant differences between irrigation treatments were only detected with WP-TSEB, and only observed in 2021, with a higher WP-TSEB under severe stress conditions.

3.7. Long-term almond water productivity

Kernel yield in 2011 had the lowest values, averaging 732.3 kg ha⁻¹, already showing significant differences between production systems (Fig. 7a). Hedgerow and central axis had significantly higher values than open vase and open vase (MP). During the period 2012 to 2016, kernel yield progressively increased until reaching maximum values in 2016. Mean values for the period 2016 to 2018 were 2789.2, 3575.2, 3205.0 and 3818.3 kg ha⁻¹, respectively for open vase, open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow. Except for 2015 and 2017, open vase consistently had significantly lower kernel yield values between 2011 and 2018. Kernel yield started progressively declining in 2019 (ten years after planting) with mean values of 2375.3 kg ha⁻¹ in 2019 and 2748.85 kg ha⁻¹ in 2020. Finally, as previously explained, kernel yield in 2021 and 2022 was very low due to major frost events. Overall, the cumulative values of kernel yield for the last twelve years indicate that open vase had significantly lower yields, but no differences were observed between the other systems (Fig. 7b). Significant differences in seasonal transpiration were observed between production systems throughout all the years assessed (Fig. 7c). Mean seasonal transpiration values for the last seven years were significantly lower for the hedgerow system, with a mean of 677.4 mm year⁻¹ (Fig. 7d). Open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis had seasonal mean values of 743.0, 903.5 and 796.9 mm year⁻¹, respectively. The hedgerow system consistently presented significantly higher WP, with significant differences between production systems before 2019 (Fig. 7e). The central axis system had the lowest significantly different WP only in 2017. The WP under fully irrigated conditions from 2016 to 2022 was significantly higher in the hedgerow production system (0.463 kg m⁻³), with open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis having historical mean WP values of 0.331, 0.345 and 0.365 (kg m⁻³), respectively (Fig. 7f).

4. Discussion

Crop water requirements mostly respond to canopy development and evaporative demand, quantified as ETo (Espadafor et al., 2015). Canopy development, however, is a function of leaf area or fIPARd, as previously described in some works (Ayars et al., 2003; Espadafor et al., 2015; Marsal et al., 2014). Therefore, since trees with different canopy structures, training systems and/or planting distances may have different leaf area and/or fIPARd values (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019; Iglesias and

Table 5

Analysis of variance (three-way ANOVA) testing the effect of year, production system (PS) and irrigation treatment (TRT) on yield components, and water productivity calculated with the two methodologies used to obtain transpiration (WP-SF and WP-TSEB).

Source	Year	PS	TRT	PSxYear	TRTxYear	PSxTRT	PSxTRTxYear
Kernel Yield	0.0299	<0.0001	ns	<0.0001	ns	ns	ns
Kernel Yield / Canopy Volume	0.0008	<0.0001	ns	0.0002	ns	ns	ns
Shelling Percentage	ns	<0.0001	<0.0001	ns	ns	ns	ns
Kernel Weight	0.0204	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0001	ns	ns	ns
Nut Load	0.0174	<0.0001	ns	<0.0001	ns	ns	ns
WP-SF	0.0198	0.0002	ns	0.0164	ns	ns	ns
WP-TSEB	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0005	0.0009	0.0005	ns	ns

Table 6

Differences in kernel yield components, and water productivity using cumulative transpiration data from sap flow sensors (WP-SF) and from remote sensing with the TSEB modelling approach (WP-TSEB), between production systems under different irrigation treatments for the growing seasons 2021 and 2022. Different letters mean significant differences at p-value < 0.05 using Tukey's honest significant difference test considering the interaction between production system and irrigation treatment with year.

Yield Components	Year	Production Systems				Irrigation Treatments		
		Open Vase	Open Vase (MP)	Central Axis	Hedgerow	Fully Irrigated	Mild Stress	Severe Stress
Kernel Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	2021	1062 b	1252 ab	1250 ab	1600 a	1333	1224	1316
	2022	696 c	1747 a	935 b	1115 b	1295	1176	899
Kernel Yield / Canopy Volume (kg m ⁻³)	2021	0.037 c	0.046 b	0.054 ab	0.072 a	0.054	0.044	0.058
	2022	0.024 b	0.051 a	0.041 ab	0.049 a	0.047	0.038	0.038
Shelling Percentage (%)	2021	33.3a	32.8 a	31.6 b	30.0 b	33.1 a	31.8 b	30.3 c
	2022	33.1 a	31.8 a	30.9 a	29.3 b	32.6 a	31.6 ab	30.2 b
Kernel Weight (g)	2021	1.73a	1.64 a	1.52 b	1.42 c	1.65 a	1.61 a	1.47 b
	2022	1.80 a	1.50 b	1.59 b	1.56 b	1.67 a	1.64 ab	1.56 b
Nut Load (nuts ha ⁻¹)	2021	612,137 b	773,008 b	820,539 b	1,133,548 a	813,504	775,856	915,064
	2022	386,965 c	1,134,457 a	581,748 bc	718,591 b	781,902	735,842	598,578

Fig. 6. Differences in water productivity between production systems and irrigation treatments calculated using sap flow transpiration (WP-SF) and TSEB transpiration (WP-TSEB). The graphs show averaged values categorized in (a) and (c) by the interaction between year and production system, and in (b) and (d) by the interaction between year and irrigation treatment. Different letters respectively indicate significant differences between production systems and irrigation treatments within each year at p-value < 0.05 using Tukey's test.

Echeverria, 2022), it is hypothesized they would also have different transpiration rates. This study reveals that the hedgerow production system consistently exhibited lower transpiration rates across all irrigation treatments during the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons, while the

open vase (MP) system showed the highest. This finding, however, may be unexpected looking only at the biophysical variable LAI since there is no direct correlation with the transpiration rates of each production system (Table 4). For instance, although the hedgerow system showed

Fig. 7. Long-term series of: (a) kernel yield during the period 2011 to 2022; and (b) cumulative kernel yield during this period (right); (c) seasonal transpiration for years 2016 to 2022; and (d) mean values for the same period (right); (e) water productivity (WP) for years 2016 to 2022; and (f) mean values for the same period (right), for each production system under fully irrigated conditions. Different letters indicate significant differences between production systems within each year at p -value < 0.05 using Tukey's test.

the lowest transpiration rates, it also had medium/high LAI values. Instead, transpiration was better correlated with fc and $fIPARd$. This can be explained by differences in the canopy clumping index between production systems, which predominantly affects the fc and $fIPARd$ (Parry et al., 2019). The higher clumping index and lower fc of the hedgerow system probably reduced the incoming shortwave radiation absorbed by the canopy, thereby limiting the energy available for transpiration.

The two methodologies used in this study to assess canopy

transpiration (sap flow and the TSEB surface energy balance model with remote sensing) showed similar trends, although T-TSEB was found to be more sensitive to inter-year changes. Therefore, the robustness of the results obtained confirms the hypothesis raised in this study regarding differences in almond water needs between production systems. The main advantage of using sap flow sensors is that, once calibrated, they provide continuous measurements of transpiration. Several studies have successfully used them in almond trees (Espadafor et al., 2015; López-López et al., 2018; Quintanilla-Albornoz et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, the main limitation is that very few trees can be monitored, especially given the need for sensor calibration to ensure actual transpiration measurement (López-Bernal et al., 2010). On the other hand, remote sensing and in particular, the use of surface energy balance models such as the TSEB with UAV imagery, allows a greater number of trees to be monitored and hence greater representativeness. In our study, this was crucial since the coefficient of variation of transpiration within each block ranged from 6.33 % to 38.83 %. The use of a remote sensing approach allowed greater statistical sample size and to mitigate errors linked to the selection of non-representative trees.

The open vase production system exhibited the lowest kernel yield (kg ha^{-1}) in both studied years. This contrasts with the findings of Casanova-Gascón et al. (2019), who reported higher kernel yields in open vase ($278 \text{ trees ha}^{-1}$) compared to super high-density systems ($2500 \text{ trees ha}^{-1}$). However, the same study also reported that yield per canopy volume in the open vase system amounted to half that of the super high-density system. In this case, our findings were similar and indicate that the open vase system had the lowest kernel yield per m^3 of canopy volume (Table 6). Conversely, and despite not being significant, the hedgerow system tended to have a higher kernel yield per canopy volume as well as a similar kernel yield compared to the open vase (MP) and central axis systems. A possible explanation for the higher kernel yield of the hedgerow production system despite its lower transpiration rates may be a better productive structure (spurs, brindles and one-year old shoots) inside the canopy volume or the *fc*. This structure likely enhances light among fruits and reproductive organs, resulting in a decreased unproductive absorbed radiation (Lampinen et al. 2012; Gradziel et al. 2017; Casanova-Gascón et al. 2019). This productive structure is created with a pruning both in winter and in spring-summer, maintaining the shape and size of the fruit wall or hedgerow, but promoting high levels of branching with a large number of spurs and brindles (Montesinos et al., 2024). In contrast, although canopy volume in the open vase training system is larger, there are empty spaces that are unproductive due to a lack of intercepted radiation, and therefore with a lot of wood production and few productive organs. The training system and pruning method play significant roles in determining the proportion of shoot types produced and may influence vegetative vigor, particularly depending on the timing and severity of pruning (Negrón et al., 2015).

Although kernel yield was not significant in the interaction of irrigation treatment and year (Table 5), it was observed that kernel yield of the severe stress treatment in 2022 was lower in comparison to the other treatments (Table 6). Other studies have also reported negative carry-over effects due to severe water stress, with significant reductions in kernel yield (Egea et al., 2010; López-López et al., 2018; Moldero et al., 2022). These studies reported, however, higher reductions in kernel yield due to water stress than those observed in our study, although the differences may be attributable to the greater stress the trees were subjected to. Nonetheless, kernel yield and nut load in our study were reduced by 31.6 % and 34.5 %, respectively, in 2022 due to the carry-over effects of severe water stress (Table 6). Furthermore, shelling percentage and kernel weight for the severe stress treatment were significantly lower than for the fully irrigated treatment in both years. This supports the observations of Girona et al. (2005); Egea et al. (2010); Goldhamer and Fereres (2017) and Moldero et al. (2021), who concluded that water deficits during the shell + hull growth and the kernel-filling stages promote a significant reduction in kernel weight. This reduction is attributed to a decrease in the photosynthetic capacity of leaves during kernel filling, allowing other tree organs to effectively compete as assimilate sinks (Egea et al., 2010).

The highest WP was observed in the hedgerow production system throughout both studied years. This explains how production system was able to produce the same kernel yield as the others while significantly using less water. In particular, under fully irrigated conditions, transpiration (measured with the sap flow approach) was 15.6 %, 29.4 %, and 11.4 % less than the open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis systems, respectively. Similarly, lower transpiration values were also

observed in the hedgerow production system using the remote sensing approach with the TSEB modelling scheme, which found 14.7 %, 26.5 % and 17.2 % less transpiration on average than the open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis systems, respectively. The adoption of severe deficit irrigation also had an impact on the WP (Table 6). It was observed that WP in the severe stress treatment was higher than in the others, although not always significant. This was more evident in 2021 using the WP-TSEB than the WP-SF approach. These results concur with those reported by Egea et al. (2010), who observed an increase in WP in trees subjected to three years of deficit irrigation. However, it is important to note that Egea et al. (2010) estimated WP as a ratio of kernel yield to applied irrigation water, which might lead to an overestimation of WP. In contrast, the novelty of our study is that we estimated WP with actual transpiration. The lower WP of the severe stress treatment in 2022 can primarily be attributed to the decreases in nut load, alongside reductions in other factors such as shelling percentage and kernel weight, as also observed by Egea et al. (2010); López-López et al. (2018) and Moldero et al. (2021). However, these studies also demonstrated that kernel yield and WP remains relatively constant in almond trees under deficit irrigation techniques for several consecutive seasons.

Since kernel yield of 2021 and 2022 was very low due to frosts, and may affect the robustness of the final conclusions, a deeper analysis was carried out looking also at historical data. Overall, no significant differences in kernel yield were observed between the open vase (MP), central axis and hedgerow systems looking at historical series of the last twelve years (Fig. 7a). The open vase production system was the only one with a significantly lower kernel yield when considering cumulative values of the period 2011–2022 (Fig. 7b). However, the lowest values were mostly observed during the first six years analyzed (2011 to 2016). This can be attributed to the lower number of trees planted per hectare, which accounted for a lower *fc* in comparison to other production systems. However, when the almond trees reached maturity and vegetative growth potential (2017–2022), no significant differences in kernel yield were observed between the production systems. In terms of transpiration, when only analyzing fully irrigated mature trees of each production system, significant differences were found between production systems during the period 2016 to 2022 (Fig. 7c). It was assumed that *fc* varied little over the last seven years. Overall, mean transpiration of the hedgerow production system for this period was 29 %, 18 % and 11 % lower than the open vase (MP), open vase and central axis systems, respectively. These differences also had a significant effect on long-term WP (Fig. 7e). The analysis of WP for the period 2016–2022 concluded that the hedgerow production system had the significantly highest historical mean WP. This higher WP was mostly observed during the period 2016 to 2018. Nevertheless, yield tend to decline after ten year of plantation (2019), diminishing therefore also WP. It is necessary to take into account that the pronounced decline in yield for 2021 and 2022 was due to a frost. Further long-term studies should be carried out to evaluate this issue in more detail. For comparison purposes, WP values obtained in the open vase system were similar to those in other studies with variations between 0.3 and 0.35 kg m^{-3} (Egea et al., 2010; Goldhamer and Fereres, 2017; López-López et al., 2018; Moldero et al., 2021).

The conclusions obtained in this study are highly relevant for the almond sector in a scenario of global warming and water shortage. For the first time, it has been scientifically shown that almond trees planted in more intensive systems (hedgerow with a planting distance of $4.5 \times 3 \text{ m}$) need less water and have a higher WP. This can undoubtedly mean a paradigm shift when planting new orchards. It should also be noted that in recent years and in some areas in Spain there is a growing popularity for the planting of super high-density almond orchards with planting distances of around $3.5 \times 1.25 \text{ m}$, which are denser than those evaluated in this study. Some studies have reported kernel yields ranging from 1325 to 2120 kg ha^{-1} in this type of super high-density orchard (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019; Iglesias and Torrents, 2022; Miarnau et al., 2022). Although kernel yields may be slightly lower compared to those reported in our study under the different production systems, it is

possible that the crop's water requirements may also be lower due to a lower *fc*. Therefore, the higher WP obtained in this study in high-density almond systems could be an additional advantage, complementing its already well-known benefits related to mechanization, reduced labor costs, early bearing, increased efficiency of phytosanitary treatments, and minimization of soil maintenance (Casanova-Gascón et al., 2019). Future studies should address this issue, adopting the technologies used in this study to assess WP in these more intensive or super-intensive production systems.

5. Conclusions

This study provides a novel contribution for the almond production sector with respect to the assessment of the water productivity of different production systems under three irrigation regimes. This is particularly relevant in the current scenario of water scarcity given the need to investigate production systems that are more efficient in the use of water and that can be adopted in areas with a Mediterranean climate in a global warming scenario.

Canopy transpiration was continuously measured with sap flow sensors and estimated through the remote sensing TSEB modelling approach during two growing seasons, giving similar results. The hedgerow production system consistently had lower transpiration rates than the others in all the irrigation treatments. On the other hand, no significant differences were observed in kernel yield between the hedgerow, central axis, and open vase (MP) systems, although the latter was slightly higher only in 2022. Although no statistical differences in kernel yield were observed between irrigation treatments, it was found in 2022 that kernel yield and nut load in the severe stress treatment were reduced by 31.6 % and 34.5 %, respectively, due to the carry-over effects of severe water stress.

The highest WP was observed in the hedgerow system throughout 2021 and 2022. In particular, under fully irrigated conditions, transpiration (measured with the sap flow approach) was 15.6 %, 29.4 %, and 11.4 % less than the open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis systems, respectively, and maintained high kernel yields. The long-term analysis for the period 2016 to 2022 also confirmed that the hedgerow production system had a significantly higher WP (0.43 kg kernel yield / m³ water transpired) than the open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis systems. As a conclusion, after the data analysis of almond trees with twelve years of productivity, it can be confirmed that the hedgerow production system had a significantly higher historical mean WP compared to the open vase, open vase (MP) and central axis systems. Future studies should aim to investigate this issue in more intensive or super-intensive production systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Manuel Quintanilla-Albornoz: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Joaquim Bellvert:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ana Pelechá:** Resources. **Xavier Miarnau:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

This research has been supported by the projects ET4DROUGHT (No. PID2021-127345OR-C31) and DIGISPAC (TED2021-131237B-C21), both funded by the Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN-AEI) of Spain, and by a mobility grant in the Incentives for Research Program 2024 of the IRTA.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank all the Efficient Use of Water in Agriculture and Fruit Production program teams at the Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA) for their technical support, especially Laura Torguet, Omar Garcia-Tejera, Mercè Mata, Carles Paris, Ramón Girabet and Aurica Biru. We would also like to express our gratitude to the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (H2020) of the European Commission, in the context of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) action and ACCWA project: grant agreement No.: 823965.

References

- Allen, R. Pereira, L., Raes, D. Smith, M., 1998. Crops evapotranspiration: guidelines for computing crop water requirements. FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 56. FAO, Rome, Italy, 300.
- Allen, R., Tasumi, M., Morse, A., Trezza, R., Wright, J.L., Bastiaanssen, W., Kramber, W., Lorite, I., Robison, C.W., 2007. Satellite-based energy balance for mapping evapotranspiration with internalized calibration (METRIC)—Applications. *J. Irrig. Drain. Eng.* 133, 395–406. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)0733-9437\(2007\)133:4\(395\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)0733-9437(2007)133:4(395)).
- ASG, 2023. El Canal Segarra-garrigues tanca fins dimarts el subministrament d'aigua. <https://www.aiguessegarragarrigues.cat/ca/2023/04/29/bombament-de-cubells-abril-5/> (accessed 13 March 2024).
- Auzmendi, I., Mata, M., del Campo, J., Lopez, G., Girona, J., Marsal, J., 2023. Relationship between daily intercepted radiation and tree transpiration in pear. *Acta Hort.* 1373, 35–42. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2023.1373.6>.
- Ayars, J.E., Johnson, R.S., Phene, C.J., Trout, T.J., Clark, D.A., Mead, R.M., 2003. Water use by drip-irrigated late-season peaches. *Irrig. Sci.* 22, 187–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-003-0084-4>.
- Bellvert, J., Nieto, H., Pelechá, A., Jofre-Čekalović, C., Zazurca, L., Miarnau, X., 2021. Remote sensing Energy balance model for the assessment of crop evapotranspiration and water status in an almond rootstock collection. *Front. Plant Sci.* 12 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.608967>.
- Ben Yahmed, J., Ghrab, M., Ben Mimoun, M., 2016. Eco-physiological evaluation of different scion-rootstock combinations of almond grown in Mediterranean conditions. *Fruits* 71, 185–193. <https://doi.org/10.1051/fruits/2016003>.
- Campbell, G., Norman, J., 1998. *An Introduction to Environmental Biophysics*. Springer, New York second ed.
- Casadesús, J., Mata, M., Marsal, J., Girona, J., 2011. Automated irrigation of apple trees based on measurements of light interception by the canopy. *Biosyst. Eng.* 108, 220–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2010.12.004>.
- Casanova-Gascón, J., Figueras-Panillo, M., Iglesias-Castellarnau, I., Martín-Ramos, P., 2019. Comparison of SHD and open-center training systems in almond tree orchards cv. 'Soleta.' *Agronomy* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy9120874>.
- DeJong, T.M., Johnson, R.S., Doyle, J.F., Ramming, D., 2005. Labor costs may be reduced Research yields size-controlling rootstocks for peach production. *Calif. Agric.* 59, 80–83. <https://doi.org/10.3733/ca.v059n02p80>.
- Drexler, J.Z., Snyder, R.L., Spano, D., Paw U, K.T., 2004. A review of models and micrometeorological methods used to estimate wetland evapotranspiration. *Hydrol. Process.* 18, 2071–2101. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.1462>.
- Egea, G., Nortes, P.A., González-Real, M.M., Baille, A., Domingo, R., 2010. Agronomic response and water productivity of almond trees under contrasted deficit irrigation regimes. *Agric. Water Manag.* 97, 171–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2009.09.006>.
- Espadafor, M., Orgaz, F., Testi, L., Lorite, L.J., Villalobos, F.J., 2015. Transpiration of young almond trees in relation to intercepted radiation. *Irrig. Sci.* 33, 265–275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-015-0464-6>.
- Fereres, E., Pruitt, W., Beutel, J., Henderson, D., Holzzapfel, E., Schulbach, H., Uriu, K., 1981. Evapotranspiration and drip irrigation scheduling (Ed.). In: Fereres, E. (Ed.), *Drip Irrigation Management*. Leaflet 21259. Division of Agricultural Science. University of California, pp. 8–13.
- Fereres, E., Soriano, M.A., 2007. Deficit irrigation for reducing agricultural water use. *J. Exp. Bot.* 58, 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erl165>.
- Fernández, E., Palomo, M., Díaz-Espejo, A., Clothier, B., Green, S., Girón, I., Moreno, F., 2001. Heat-pulse measurements of sap flow in olives for automating irrigation: tests, root flow and diagnostics of water stress. *Agric. Water Manag.* 51, 99–123.
- Fernández, E., 2023. Editorial note on terms for crop evapotranspiration, water use efficiency and water productivity. *Agric. Water Manag.* 289, 2021–2023. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108548>.
- Gao, R., Torres-Rua, A., Nieto, H., Zahn, E., Hipps, L., Kustas, W., Alsina, M., Bambach, N., Castro, S., Prueger, J., Alfieri, J., McKee, L., White, W., Gao, F., McElrone, A., Anderson, M., Knipper, K., Coopmans, C., Gowing, I., Agam, N., Sanchez, L., Dokoozlian, N., 2023. ET partitioning assessment using the TSEB model

- and sUAS information across California central valley vineyards. *Remote Sens.* 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15030756>.
- Gaona, J., Quintana-Seguí, P., Escorihuela, M., Boone, A., Llasat, M., 2022. Interactions between precipitation, evapotranspiration and soil-moisture-based indices to characterize drought with high-resolution remote sensing and land-surface model data. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 22, 3461–3485. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-3461-2022>.
- Girona, J., Mata, M., Del Campo, J., Arbonés, A., Bartra, E., Marsal, J., 2006. The use of midday leaf water potential for scheduling deficit irrigation in vineyards. *Irrig. Sci.* 24, 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-005-0015-7>.
- Girona, J., Mata, M., Marsal, J., 2005. Regulated deficit irrigation during the kernel-filling period and optimal irrigation rates in almond. *Agric. Water Manag.* 75, 152–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2004.12.008>.
- Goldammer, D., Fereres, E., 2017. Establishing an almond water production function for California using long-term yield response to variable irrigation. *Irrig. Sci.* 35, 169–179. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-016-0528-2>.
- Goldammer, D., Snyder, R., 1989. *Irrigation scheduling: a guide for efficient on-farm water management*. Univ. Calif. Div. Agr. Nat. Res. Publ. 21454.
- Gómez-Candón, D., Bellvert, J., Pelechá, A., Lopes, M.S., 2023. A remote sensing approach for assessing daily cumulative evapotranspiration integral in wheat genotype screening for drought adaptation. *Plants* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants12223871>.
- Gradziel, T., Curtis, R., Socias I Company, R., 2017. *Production and growing regions*. In: Gradziel, T.M. (Ed.), *almonds, botany, production, and uses*. R. Socias I Company and CAB International, Boston, MA, pp. p70–p86 eds.
- Hoedjes, J., Chehbouni, A., Jacob, F., Ezzahar, J., Boulet, G., 2008. Deriving daily evapotranspiration from remotely sensed instantaneous evaporative fraction over olive orchard in semi-arid Morocco. *J. Hydrol.* 354, 53–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2008.02.016>.
- Iglesias, I., Echeverría, G., 2022. *Scientia Horticulturae* Current situation, trends and challenges for efficient and sustainable peach production. *Sci. Hortic. (Amsterdam)* 296, 110899. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2022.110899>.
- Iglesias, I., Torrents, J., 2022. Developing high-density training systems in Prunus tree species for an efficient and sustainable production. *Acta Hortic.* 1346, 219–227. <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2022.1346.28>.
- Jackson, R., Huete, A., 1991. Interpreting vegetation indices. *Prev. Vet. Med.* 11, 185–200. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-5877\(05\)80004-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-5877(05)80004-2).
- Jofre-Čekalović, C., Nieto, H., Girona, J., Pamies-sans, M., Bellvert, J., 2022. Accounting for almond crop water use under different irrigation regimes with a two-source energy balance model and Copernicus-based inputs. *Remote Sens.* 14, e2106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14092106>.
- Kalma, J., McVicar, T., McCabe, M., 2008. Estimating land surface evaporation: a review of methods using remotely sensed surface temperature data. *Surv. Geophys.* 29, 421–469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-008-9037-z>.
- Kustas, W., Anderson, M., 2009. Advances in thermal infrared remote sensing for land surface modeling. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 149, 2071–2081. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2009.05.016>.
- Lampinen, B., Udompetaikul, V., Browne, G., Metcalf, S., Stewart, W., Contador, L., Negrón, C., Upadhyaya, S.K., 2012. A mobile platform for measuring canopy photosynthetically active radiation interception in orchard systems. *HortTechnology* 22, 237–244. <https://doi.org/10.21273/horttech.22.2.237>.
- López-Bernal, Á., Alcántara, E., Testi, L., Villalobos, F.J., 2010. Spatial sap flow and xylem anatomical characteristics in olive trees under different irrigation regimes. *Tree Physiol.* 30, 1536–1544. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/tpq095>.
- López-López, M., Espadafor, M., Testi, L., Lorite, I., Orgaz, F., Fereres, E., 2018. Yield response of almond trees to transpiration deficits. *Irrig. Sci.* 36, 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-018-0568-x>.
- Maldera, F., Vivaldi, G., Iglesias-Castellarnau, I., Camposo, S., 2021. Two almond cultivars trained in a super-high density orchard show different growth, yield efficiencies and damages by mechanical harvesting. *Agronomy* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11071406>.
- MAPA, 2023. Encuesta sobre Superficies y Rendimientos Cultivos (ESYRCE). Encuesta de marco de áreas de España. <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/estadisticas-agrarias/agricultura/esyrce/default.aspx> (accessed 13 March 2024).
- Marsal, J., Johnson, S., Casadesus, J., Lopez, G., Girona, J., Stöckle, C., 2014. Fraction of canopy intercepted radiation relates differently with crop coefficient depending on the season and the fruit tree species. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 184, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2013.08.008>.
- McCutchan, H., Shackel, K., 1992. Stem-water potential as a sensitive indicator of water stress in prune trees (*Prunus domestica* L. cv. French). *J. Am. Soc. Hortic. Sci.* 117, 607–611.
- McFeeters, K., 1996. The use of the normalized difference water index (NDWI) in the delineation of open water features. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 17, 1425–1432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431169608948714>.
- Miarnau, X., Maldonado, M., Girabet, R., Zazurca, L., Martínez, G., Torguet, L., 2022. *Claves para la futura rentabilidad del almendro*. *Vida Rural* 514, 38–44.
- Moldero, D., López-Bernal, Á., Testi, L., Lorite, I., Fereres, E., Orgaz, F., 2021. Long-term almond yield response to deficit irrigation. *Irrig. Sci.* 39, 409–420. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-021-00720-8>.
- Moldero, D., López-Bernal, Á., Testi, L., Lorite, I., Fereres, E., Orgaz, F., 2022. Almond responses to a single season of severe irrigation water restrictions. *Irrig. Sci.* 40, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-021-00750-2>.
- Montesinos, Á., Maldera, F., Thorp, G.T., Rubio-Cabetas, M., 2024. Scion–rootstock combination determines pruning responses in young almond trees. *HortScience* 59, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI117423-23>.
- Myers, B., 1998. Water stress integral—A link between short-term stress and long-term growth. *Tree Physiol.* 4, 315–323. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/4.4.315>.
- Negrón, C., Contador, L., Lampinen, B., Metcalf, S., Guédon, Y., Costes, E., DeJong, T., 2015. How different pruning severities alter shoot structure: a modelling approach in young ‘Nonpareil’ almond trees. *Functional Plant Biol.* 42, 325–335. <https://doi.org/10.1071/FP14025>.
- Nieto, H., Kustas, W., Torres-Rúa, A., Alfieri, J., Gao, F., Anderson, M., White, W., Song, L., Alsina, M., Del, M., Prueger, J., McKee, M., Elarab, M., McKee, L., 2019. Evaluation of TSEB turbulent fluxes using different methods for the retrieval of soil and canopy component temperatures from UAV thermal and multispectral imagery. *Irrig. Sci.* 37, 389–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-018-0585-9>.
- Norman, J., Kustas, W., Humes, K., 1995. Source approach for estimating soil and vegetation energy fluxes in observations of directional radiometric surface temperature. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 77, 263–293. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923\(95\)02265-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1923(95)02265-Y).
- Noun, G., Lo Cascio, M., Spano, D., Marras, S., Sirca, C., 2022. Plant-based methodologies and approaches for estimating plant water status of mediterranean tree species: a semi-systematic review. *Agronomy* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12092127>.
- Olivo, N., Girona, J., Marsal, J., 2009. Seasonal sensitivity of stem water potential to vapour pressure deficit in grapevine. *Irrig. Sci.* 27, 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-008-0134-z>.
- Overgaard, J., Rosbjerg, D., Butts, M., 2006. Land-surface modelling in hydrological perspective - A review. *Biogeosciences* 3, 229–241. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-3-229-2006>.
- Parry, C., Nieto, H., Guillevic, P., Agam, N., Kustas, W., Alfieri, J., McKee, L., McElrone, A., 2019. An intercomparison of radiation partitioning models in vineyard canopies. *Irrig. Sci.* 37, 239–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-019-00621-x>.
- Peddinti, S., Kisekka, I., 2022. Estimation of turbulent fluxes over almond orchards using high-resolution aerial imagery with one and two-source energy balance models. *Agric. Water Manag.* 269, 107671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2022.107671>.
- Qi, J., Chehbouni, A., Huete, A., Kerr, Y., Sorooshian, S., 1994. A modified soil adjusted vegetation index. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 48, 119–126. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257\(94\)90134-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257(94)90134-1).
- Quintanilla-Albornoz, M., Miarnau, X., Pelechá, A., Casadesús, J., García-Tejera, O., Bellvert, J., 2023. Evaluation of transpiration in different almond production systems with two-source energy balance models from UAV thermal and multispectral imagery. *Irrig. Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-023-00888-1>.
- Quintanilla-Albornoz, M., Miarnau, X., Pelechá, A., Nieto, H., Bellvert, J., 2024. Assessment of upscaling methodologies for daily crop transpiration using sap-flows and two-source energy balance models in almonds under different water status and production systems. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Discuss.* <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-2024-5> [preprint].
- Ramírez-Cuesta, J., Intrigliolo, D., Lorite, I., Moreno, M., Vanella, D., Ballesteros, R., Hernández-López, D., Buesa, I., 2023. Determining grapevine water use under different sustainable agronomic practices using METRIC-UAV surface energy balance model. *Agric. Water Manag.* 281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108247>.
- Reig, G., Lordan, J., Hoying, S., Fargione, M., Donahue, D.J., Francescato, P., Acimovic, D., Fazio, G., Robinson, T., 2020. Long-term performance of ‘delicious’ apple trees grafted on Geneva® rootstocks and trained to four high-density systems under New York state climatic conditions. *HortScience* 55, 1538–1550. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI14904-20>.
- Shuttleworth, W., Wallace, J., 1985. Evaporation from sparse crops—an energy combination theory. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* 111, 839–855. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.49711146510>.
- Smith, D., Allen, S., 1996. Measurement of sap flow in plant stems. *J. Exp. Bot.* 47, 1833–1844. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/47.12.1833>.
- Tramblay, Y., Koutroulis, A., Samaniego, L., Vicente-Serrano, S., Volaire, F., Boone, A., Le Page, M., Llasat, M., Albergel, C., Burak, S., Cailleret, M., Kalin, K., Davi, H., Dupuy, J., Greve, P., Grillakis, M., Hanich, L., Jarlan, L., Martin-StPaul, N., Martínez-Vilalta, J., Mouillot, F., Pulido-Velazquez, D., Quintana-Seguí, P., Renard, D., Turco, M., Türkeş, M., Trigo, R., Vidal, J., Vilagrosa, A., Zribi, M., Polcher, J., 2020. Challenges for drought assessment in the Mediterranean region under future climate scenarios. *Earth-Sci. Rev.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103348>.
- USDA-NASS, 2022. 2022 California almond objective measurement report. https://www.nass.usda.gov/Statistics_by_State/California/Publications/Specialty_and_Other_Releases/Almond/Objective-Measurement/2023almondOM.pdf (accessed 13 March 2024).
- Villalobos, F., Testi, L., Moreno-Perez, M., 2009. Evaporation and canopy conductance of citrus orchards. *Agric. Water Manag.* 96, 565–573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2008.09.016>.
- Xing, N., Huang, W., Xie, Q., Shi, Y., Ye, H., Dong, Y., Wu, M., Sun, G., Jiao, Q., 2020. A transformed triangular vegetation index for estimating winter wheat leaf area index. *Remote Sens.* 12, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS12010016>.